

Consumers Awareness towards Green Marketing and Consumer Perception and Preferences in Varanasi

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Abstract:- The green movement is quickly growing around the world. Consumers accept responsibility and act responsibly in this regard. Consumer awareness and inspiration continue to drive market transformation, particularly with the launch of more environmentally friendly products. The key to successful marketing has always been to recognize trends and frame goods, brands, and services in ways that support customer intentions. Many firms have expressed concern about environmental issues. Companies are coming up with more green products that help to improve the world's polluted conditions. They "go green" as they realize that they can decrease pollution issues and at the same time grow profits. Environmental marketing, or green marketing, aims to protect the environment for upcoming generations.

This paper highlights consumer awareness of green marketing and the perception of consumers with the help of a questionnaire. A survey of 100 respondents was conducted. According to the results of this survey, there are growing concerns about consumer awareness, the environment, and a growing preference for green products. This trend offers a chance for a marketer to offer green products and catch the theme. Keep in mind that these research-inspiring, mind-boggling facts can have a big impact on the way different companies make and sell consumer goods.

Keywords:- Green marketing, environmentally friendly products, consumer purchasing behavior, and the environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

The term "marketing" is moving towards consumer satisfaction and environmental protection through the advertising campaigns of almost every major business house across the globe.

"Green marketing," according to Polonsky (1994), is defined as "all activities designed to generate and facilitate any exchange intended to satisfy human needs or wants such that satisfying their needs and wants occurs with minimal detrimental input on the national environment." It's the marketing of goods that are presumably environmentally safe. " As a consequence, green marketing comprises a lot of different things, like changes to products, changes to production processes, changes to packaging, and changes to advertising.

Because resources are limited and human wants are limitless, marketers must use resources effectively and avoid wasting them to achieve the organization's objectives. As a result, green marketing is unavoidable. Environmental concerns are becoming increasingly important to people all over the globe. Consumers are environmentally conscious and are shifting their attitudes and behaviors accordingly to universal evidence. As a result, green marketing has emerged to address the increased demand for environmentally friendly and socially responsible goods and services. Consumers are more concerned than ever before about environmental deterioration and the negative impact their purchases have on the environment. Marketers now say that meeting the needs of customers according to environmental concerns and making more money is their new goal.

As a result, a study of consumer attitudes and awareness regarding green products is critical. This study's purpose is to find out the level of consumer awareness and their perceptions of environmentally friendly products.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mahesh and P. Gomathi (2016) conducted "A Study on Rural Consumers' Buying Behavior of Green Products with special reference to selected villages in Tirupur." The researchers looked into environmental concerns and the factors that influence consumer purchasing of environmentally friendly products. The majority of the respondents are males, as they are graduates. They prefer green products. Price is the main factor that prevents purchasing green products. Lack of awareness and green product availability are also factors preventing consumers from purchasing green products.

Dr. Seema Laddha and Prof. Mayur Malviya (2015) collected primary data from 150 Navy Mumbai samples for their study "Green Marketing and its Impact on Consumer Buying Behavior." The respondents were asked questions about the environment and buying behavior. This survey identified environmental problems and also consumer awareness of eco-friendly products. The majority of consumers are willing to buy that product, which companies use to satisfy their electricity needs from renewable sources.

Bhatia Mayank and Amit Jain (2013) conducted a brief evaluation of the environmental issues to identify consumers' green values, level of awareness about environmental problems, green products, and green practices. This study examines consumer perceptions and preferences toward green marketing practices and products using a structured questionnaire. It included 106 respondents. According to the results of the study, green

values, knowledge about green products, and the perception that marketing companies are serious about green marketing all played a significant role in making consumers want to buy and prefer green products over conventional items.

Altaf N. (2003) conducted "Consumers' awareness Towards Green Marketing—a Study of Srinagar City" According to the study, consumers are increasingly concerned with the concept of green marketing and companies' going green. Consumers in Srinagar city filled out a questionnaire with a sample size of 100 people.

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Attitudes are changing toward the environment to boost innovation for conservation. The green movement is rapidly growing around the world. These consumers are concerned about protecting the environment by avoiding plastics and other harmful items that affect the environment, causing global warming, loss of biodiversity, pollution, and deforestation. The government has to take initiatives to reduce the negative effects of a company's products or services to make the environment friendlier and create awareness about green products. This paper studies consumers' awareness of green marketing and the use of eco-friendly products.

A. Objectives of this study

- To study the awareness level of consumers toward green marketing.
- To study the influence of various demographic factors on green marketing
- To investigate the preferences of Varanasi consumers about green products.
- To measure the green values of the consumers

B. Hypothesis:

a) First Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant difference (strong association) among various demographic factors with awareness level of the consumers towards Green Marketing.

H₁: There is a significant difference (no association) among various demographic factors with awareness level of the consumers towards Green Marketing.

b) Second Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant difference in green values on the basis of gender

H₁: There is a significant difference in green values on the basis of gender

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study attempts to realize consumer attitudes towards green marketing in Varanasi. Primary and secondary sources of data were used to conduct this study. Primary data was collected from 100 respondents in the Varanasi U.P. The questionnaire was designed for a sample of 100 respondents from Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, representing both genders, different age groups, education levels, and annual income. A structured questionnaire with a five-point balanced Likert scale was used to measure consumer attitudes toward green marketing and the perception of eco-friendly products. Using mean score analysis and percentage, the collection of data from respondents is tabulated and analyzed into logical reports. The primary data was collected and analyzed with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 20. To obtain the findings of the primary data analysis using the Kruskal-Wallis test, the following statistical tools were used in the study: The Cronbach's Alpha Criterion was applied. Due to COVID-19 Pandemic Questionnaire was put up online on the social media platform. Secondary sources from available literature, journals, papers, and books.

Data Analysis and Interpretation: Five major socio-economic factors were taken for studies the gender of respondents, age group, education level, annual income, and occupation.

S.no	Variables		No. of respondents (100)	Percentage
1.	Gender	Male	46	46
		Female	54	54
2.	Age Group	Below 18	5	5
		18 to 30	45	45
		31 to 45	38	38
		46 to 60	10	10
		61 and above	2	2
3.	Educational Qualification	Illiterate	0	0
		Primary	6	6
		Secondary	8	8
		Graduate	21	21
		Post Graduate	48	48
		Professional Degree	8	8
		Doctorate and Others	9	9
4.	Annual Income (In Rupees.)	Up to 1,00,000	35	35
		1,00,001 to 3,00,000	44	44
		3,00,001 to 5,00,000	14	14
		Above 5,00,000	7	7
5.	Occupation	Agriculture	1	1
		Business/ Self employment	14	14
		Private Employee	40	40
		Government employee	9	9
		Student	36	36

Table 1: Socio-economic status of consumers

The above table 1 clearly shows the socioeconomic level of respondents, out of 100 respondents,

- The majority (54%) of the respondents are female.
- The majority (45%) of respondents belong to the age group of 18–30 years.
- The majority (48%) of the respondents are qualified as post-graduate.
- The majority (44%) of the respondents are earning an annual income which lies between Rs.100001- Rs.30000
- The majority (40%) of the respondents are private employees.

Response	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	86	86
No	4	4
A little	10	10
Total	100	100

Table 2: Awareness level of consumers about green marketing

Fig. 1: Awareness level of consumers about green marketing

The majority of respondents (86 percent) are aware of green marketing.

Response	Number of Respondents	Percentage
YES	90	90
NO	3	3
A little	7	7
Total	100	100

Table 3: Awareness level of consumers about green products or Eco-friendly products

Fig. 2: Awareness level of consumers about green products or Eco-friendly products

The majority of respondents (90 percent) are aware of eco-friendly or "green" products.

Response	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Television	69	69
Magazines	3	3
Class lectures	11	11
Newspapers	8	8
others	9	9
Total	100	100

Table 4: Consumers source of awareness about "green products" or eco-friendly products

Fig. 3: Consumers source of awareness about "green products" or eco-friendly products

The majority (69%) of consumers became aware by television to purchase eco-friendly products.

Awareness of consumers towards Green Marketing with possible responses of "strongly agree," "agree," "slightly agree," "disagree and "strongly disagree"

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	31	4.28
4	Agree	66	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	3	
2	Disagree	0	
1	Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL		100	

Table 5: Frequency of consumer Believing in The Concept of Green Marketing

Fig. 4: Frequency of consumer Believing in The Concept of Green Marketing

Table 5 shows that respondents agree on the concept of green marketing, with a computed mean score of 4.28. We can infer that consumers strongly believe in green marketing.

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	16	4.03
4	Agree	71	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	13	
2	Disagree	0	
1	Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL		100	

Table 6: Awareness of consumer about Companies Going Green

Fig. 5: Awareness of consumer about Companies Going Green

Table 6 shows that respondents are aware of companies' going green, with a mean score of 4.03. We can infer that consumer are paying attention to companies that are going green.

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	28	4.23
4	Agree	67	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	5	
2	Disagree	0	
1	Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL		100	

Table 7: Awareness level of consumers About the Advantages of Using Green Product

Fig. 6: Awareness level of consumers About the Advantages of Using Green Product

Table 7 shows that respondents agree on the advantages of using green products, with a mean score of 4.23. We can infer that consumer correlates their beliefs with the benefits of products that are eco-friendly.

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	13	3.87
4	Agree	70	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	8	
2	Disagree	9	
1	Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL		100	

Table 8; Consumer perception about Harmful Marketing Techniques

Fig. 7: Consumer perception about Harmful Marketing Techniques

Table 8 shows that respondents agree that regular marketing techniques may harm the environment as the mean score is 3.87. We can presume that respondents think that regular marketing techniques are not eco-friendly.

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	17	4.11
4	Agree	78	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	4	
2	Disagree	1	
1	Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL		100	

Table 9: Green Marketing Concepts exists for a Long Time Back but it is Not Implemented by Many Companies

5. Green Marketing Concepts is Existed For Long Time Back but it is Not Implemented by Many Companies
100 responses

Fig. 8: Green Marketing Concepts exists for a Long Time Back but it is Not Implemented by Many Companies

Table 9 shows that respondents think that green marketing existed a long time ago, but it was not widely implemented, with a mean score of 4.11. In this way, we can say that respondents knew about the green marketing concept before the companies implemented it.

RATING SCALE	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5 Strongly Agree	12	4.03
4 Agree	79	
3 Neither Agree nor Disagree	9	
2 Disagree	0	
1 Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL	100	

Table 10: Consumer Perception about green marketing for improving Productivity

6. Productivity can be Improved Drastically by Using Green Marketing
100 responses

Fig. 9: Consumer Perception about green marketing for improving Productivity

Table 10 shows that respondents agree that green marketing improved productivity drastically, with a mean score of 4.03. Green marketing, according to respondents, can boost productivity.

RATING SCALE	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5 Strongly Agree	8	3.96
4 Agree	80	
3 Neither Agree nor Disagree	12	
2 Disagree	0	
1 Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL	100	

Table 11: Consumer perception about Companies Reluctant in Implementing Green Marketing Concept

Fig. 10: Consumer perception about Companies Reluctant in Implementing Green Marketing Concept

Table 11 shows that respondents agree that companies are reluctantly implementing green marketing, with a mean score of 3.96. As a result, we can presume that some companies are against adopting green marketing concepts.

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	5	3.77
4	Agree	75	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	12	
2	Disagree	8	
1	Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL		100	

Table 12: Consumer perception if companies face Difficulty in Implementing Green Marketing

Fig. 11: Consumer perception if companies face Difficulty in Implementing Green Marketing

Table 12 shows that respondents agree that it is difficult for all companies to implement green marketing, with a mean score of 3.77. We can infer that some companies face difficulty in implementing green marketing.

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	8	3.81
4	Agree	75	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	8	
2	Disagree	8	
1	Strongly Disagree	1	
TOTAL		100	

Table 13: Consumer perception if Huge Investments is Required to Develop Green Products

9. Huge Investments is Required to Develop Green Product
100 responses

Fig. 12: Consumer perception if Huge Investments is Required to Develop Green Products

Table 13 shows that Respondents Agree that more investment is required to develop green products, with a mean score of 3.81. We can presume that developing green products typically costs more upfront but generate great rewards in the long run.

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	28	4.22
4	Agree	66	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	6	
2	Disagree	0	
1	Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL		100	

Table 14: Consumer perception about Government responsibility in Taking Initiating for Making Companies Go Green

10. Government Should Take Initiative in making Companies To Go Green
100 responses

Fig. 13: Consumer perception about Government responsibility in Taking INITIATING FOR Making Companies Go Green

Table 14 shows that respondents agree that the government takes the initiative in making companies go green, with a mean score of 4.22. We can presume that the government has a dominating role in promoting green companies.

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	27	4.21
4	Agree	69	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	2	
2	Disagree	2	
1	Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL		100	

Table 15: Consumer perception if Everyone is Responsible for Successful Green Marketing

Fig. 14: Consumer perception if Everyone is Responsible for Successful Green Marketing

Table 15 shows that respondents agree that for successful green marketing, everyone is responsible, with a mean score of 4.21. We can presume that each person must promote the idea of green marketing.

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	8	3.54
4	Agree	60	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	13	
2	Disagree	16	
1	Strongly Disagree	3	
TOTAL		100	

Table 16: Consumer perception if Green Marketing is Just an Old Concept

Fig. 15: Consumer perception if Green Marketing is Just an Old Concept

Table 16 shows that respondents agree that green marketing is an old concept, with a mean score of 3.54. We can infer that green marketing concepts are an old concept that involves the promotion of products and services that are safe for the environment.

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	24	4.24
4	Agree	76	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	0	
2	Disagree	0	
1	Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL		100	

Table 17: Consumer Interest In Knowing More About Green Marketing

Fig. 16: Consumer Interest In Knowing More About Green Marketing

Table 17 shows that, with a mean score of 4.24, respondents agree that they just want to know more about green marketing. We can infer that respondents are interested in green marketing.

RATING SCALE		PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS	MEAN SCORE
5	Strongly Agree	20	4.16
4	Agree	77	
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	2	
2	Disagree	1	
1	Strongly Disagree	0	
TOTAL		100	

18 Consumers Believe To The Concept Of Complete Green Marketing Conditions Throughout The World

Fig. 17: Consumers Believe To The Concept Of Complete Green Marketing Conditions Throughout The World

Table 18 shows that respondents agree, with a mean score of 4.16, that they believe in the concept of complete green marketing conditions throughout the world. In general, we can say that people believe in green marketing all over the world.

V. PERCEPTION OF CONSUMERS ABOUT ECO-FRIENDLY PRODUCTS

Perception of consumers about the environment-friendly product with possible responses of "strongly agree," "agree," "slightly agree," "disagree" and "strongly disagree."

According to the reliability analysis of the Green Consumer Scale, the Cronbach's Alpha value is .897, as shown in Table 19 below.

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.897	6

Table 19: Reliability Statistics

	Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
Green Value- 1	I am aware of the benefits of "green products" or "eco-friendly products."	4.00	.667
Green Value- 2	It is important to me that the products I use do not harm the environment.	3.98	.791
Green Value-	My purchase habits are affected by my concern for the environment.	3.88	.729
Green Value-4	I am concerned about wasting the resources of our planet.	3.99	.732
Green Value- 5	I would describe myself as environmentally responsible.	4.00	.682
Green Value-6	I am willing to be inconvenienced in order to take actions that are more environmentally friendly.	3.85	.702
	Overall Green Value	3.95	.582

Table 20: Green consumer value measure

The overall green value of the customers is determined to be 3.95, indicating that the consumers are concerned about environmental protection.

Consumers are concerned about environmental protection after understanding green marketing concepts and the perception of eco-friendly products. This paper highlights a marketing perspective on the potential for green products and the need for significant changes in the green marketing concept. If resources are used properly, the finished product that a company makes will be less harmful to the environment.

• **Kruskal-Wallis Test:**

Hypothesis 1:

H0: There is no significant difference (strong association) among various demographic factors with awareness level of the consumers towards Green Marketing.

vs.

H1: There is a significant difference (no association) among various demographic factors with awareness level of the consumers towards Green Marketing.

Awareness level of the consumers	Test Statistics					
		Gender	Age Group	Educational Qualification	Annual Income	Occupation
I Believe in The Concept of Green Marketing	Chi-Square	.086	2.503	7.165	3.014	.889
	Asymp. Sig.	.770	.644	.209	.389	.926
I am aware of Companies Going Green	Chi-Square	.020	13.717	7.216	10.357	10.050
	Asymp. Sig.	.886	.008	.205	.016	.040
I am aware About the Advantages of Using Green Product	Chi-Square	.019	4.002	2.943	1.050	1.346
	Asymp. Sig.	.890	.406	.709	.789	.854
I feel that Regular Marketing Techniques Harm the Environment	Chi-Square	4.392	8.037	4.305	4.701	4.342
	Asymp. Sig.	.036	.090	.506	.195	.362
Green Marketing Concepts is Existed for Long Time Back but it is Not Implemented by Many Companies	Chi-Square	.014	4.715	7.084	3.499	3.726
	Asymp. Sig.	.905	.318	.214	.321	.444
Productivity can be Improved Drastically by Using Green Marketing	Chi-Square	.029	8.542	12.029	3.477	17.597
	Asymp. Sig.	.865	.074	.034	.324	.001
Companies Are Reluctant in Implementing Green Marketing Concept	Chi-Square	.128	13.171	2.881	.665	7.163
	Asymp. Sig.	.721	.010	.718	.881	.128
It is difficult For All the Companies to Implement Green Marketing	Chi-Square	2.706	3.992	4.785	5.503	2.078
	Asymp. Sig.	.100	.407	.443	.138	.721
Huge Investments is Required to Develop Green Product	Chi-Square	.829	2.358	3.503	9.222	1.569
	Asymp. Sig.	.362	.670	.623	.026	.814
Government Should Take Initiative in making Companies Go Green	Chi-Square	1.437	14.916	7.277	1.213	9.945
	Asymp. Sig.	.231	.005	.201	.750	.041
Everyone is Responsible for Successful Green Marketing	Chi-Square	1.543	6.582	11.210	.454	5.774
	Asymp. Sig.	.214	.160	.047	.929	.217
Green Marketing is Just an old Concept	Chi-Square	.886	9.664	2.275	6.305	6.908
	Asymp. Sig.	.347	.046	.810	.098	.141
I am interested to Know More About Green Marketing	Chi-Square	.839	3.718	1.744	3.470	1.346
	Asymp. Sig.	.360	.446	.883	.325	.854
I Believe in The Concept of Complete Green Marketing Conditions Throughout the World	Chi-Square	.265	2.112	11.790	1.061	3.690
	Asymp. Sig.	.607	.715	.038	.786	.450

Table 21: Kruskal-Wallis Test for Awareness level of the consumer

(Source: Compiled Primary Data)

Conclusion: Highlighted part (bold) shows p-value < 0.05, hence, we reject H₀ for those particular cases (Highlighted). And conclude that there is a significant difference (no association) among various demographic factors with awareness level of the consumers towards Green Marketing.

The other parameters show p-value >0.05, hence, we do not reject H₀ in such cases and conclude that there is no significant difference (strong association) among various demographic factors with awareness level of the consumers towards Green Marketing

Demographic Factors	Not significantly different	Significantly different
Gender	No significance difference respect to other with variables	Gender wise the awareness level of consumers towards Green Marketing differs for following 1 variable: 1. I feel that regular marketing techniques harm the environment.
Age Group	No significance difference respect to other with variables	Age group wise the awareness level of consumers towards Green Marketing differs for following 4 variables: 1. I am aware of companies going green. 2. Companies Are Reluctant in Implementing Green Marketing Concept. 3. Government Should Take Initiative in Making Companies Go Green. 4. Green Marketing is Just an old Concept
Educational Qualification	No significance difference respect to other with variables	Educational Qualification wise the awareness level of consumers towards Green Marketing differs for following 3 variables: 1.Productivity can be improved drastically by using green marketing. 2.Everyone is Responsible for Successful Green Marketing 3.I Believe in The Concept of Complete Green Marketing Conditions Throughout the World.
Annual Income	No significance difference respect to other with variables	Annual Income wise the awareness level of consumers towards Green Marketing differs for following 2 variables: 1.I am aware of companies going green. 2. Huge Investments is Required to Develop Green Products.
Occupation	No significance difference respect to other with variables	Occupation wise the awareness level of consumers towards Green Marketing differs for following 3 variables: 1.I am aware of companies going green. 2. Productivity can be improved drastically by using green marketing. 3.Government Should Take Initiative in Making Companies Go Green.

Table 22: Overall Conclusion on Various Demographic Factors with Awareness Level of the Consumers towards Green Marketing.

Table 22 shows Overall Conclusion on Significant Difference among Various Demographic Factors with Awareness Level of the Consumers towards Green Marketing. It is interpreted that there is variance between demographic factors and their awareness about green marketing concept.

Hypothesis 2:

It was found that there is no significant difference in green consumer values based on gender; the overall green value of consumers was found to be **3.95** and the p-value for the overall green consumer value was found to be **0.686**, which states that the null hypothesis is accepted and it can be inferred that the gender of the consumers does not affect their green values.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

The present study examined the awareness level of green marketing and the perception of consumers toward eco-friendly products in the city of Varanasi. It is one of the world's oldest cities and is situated on the bank of the river Ganga in the state of Uttar Pradesh.

Today, consumers have become more conscious of their healthy lives and environmentalism. As a result, there is an essential for the concept of green marketing and a change in business organizations' behavior toward providing more eco-friendly products. Apart from that, consumers have revealed more worries about the concept of green marketing and companies' going green. Consumers are well aware that productivity improves drastically when green marketing is used. We can say that the government has a dominating role in promoting green companies. We can presume that some consumers agree that green marketing concepts are an old concept. We can say that the respondents have faith in the green marketing concept around the globe. The consumer is also aware of the benefits of green products. We can infer that it is crucial for all that the products they use do not harm the environment. Consumers are interested in knowing more about green marketing in the study area. The data analysis helps companies who face difficulty in implementing green marketing concepts. Everyone should have to respond to save the environment.

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